

Evaluation of Doctor's Perception About the Role of the Pharmacy in Pharmaceutical Services in Tengku Rafi'an Siak Hospital and Dr. Rasidin Padang Hospital

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Abstract:- Pharmaceutical care (pharmaceutical care) is a form of service and direct responsibility of the pharmacist profession in pharmaceutical work to determine, implement and monitor drug use in order to produce the expected therapeutic outcomes . To start a collaborative working relationship between doctors and pharmacists, it is necessary to know the doctor's perception of the pharmacist's role in the things that are expected by a doctor from a pharmacist. The various perceptions of doctors on the role of pharmacists in hospitals, it is known that the role of pharmacists is still not good in pharmaceutical services in hospitals, so it is feared that the quality of life of patients will not be achieved. This study was conducted with the aim of assessing doctors' perceptions of the role of pharmacists in pharmaceutical services at Tengku Rafi'an Siak Hospital and dr. Rasidin Padang in order to meet all patient needs. The analytical method in statistics used in analyzing research results and observations is the *analysis of variance* (ANOVA) method. Based on the results , the $\bar{x} \pm SD$ value for the gender criteria was 1.44 ± 0.498 with a total TCR of 71.85, and the $\bar{x} \pm SD$ value for the criteria for length of service was 2.22 ± 0.537 with a total TCR of 71.85, so it can be concluded that doctors' perceptions about the role of pharmacists in pharmaceutical services at Teuku Rafi'an Siak Hospital and dr. Rasidin Padang seen from the gender criteria and the length of service criteria is quite good.

Keywords:- Pharmaceutical Care, Analysis of Variance, Perception, RSUD

I. INTRODUCTION

Currently, pharmaceutical services have shifted their orientation, where previously pharmaceutical services only focused on managing drugs as a commodity, to become comprehensive services aimed at improving the quality of life of patients. Pharmacists are required to improve knowledge, skills and behavior to be able to carry out direct interactions with patients. In addition, pharmacists must be able to cooperate with other health workers in determining therapy to support rational drug use. To start a collaborative working relationship between doctors and pharmacists, it is necessary to know the doctor's perception of the pharmacist's role in the things that are expected by a doctor from a pharmacist. The

various perceptions of doctors on the role of pharmacists in hospitals, it is known that the role of pharmacists is still not good in pharmaceutical services in hospitals, so it is feared that the quality of life of patients will not be achieved. This study was conducted with the aim of assessing doctors' perceptions of the role of pharmacists in pharmaceutical services at Tengku Rafi'an Siak Hospital and dr. Rasidin Padang in order to meet all patient needs.

Perception is one of the important psychological aspects for humans in responding to the presence of various aspects and symptoms around them . *Pharmaceutical care* standards are benchmarks used as guidelines for pharmaceutical staff in providing pharmaceutical services. *Pharmaceutical care (PC) is a patient-oriented pharmaceutical service program where pharmacists work together with other health workers in carrying out health promotion, preventing disease, assessing, monitoring , plan and modify treatment to ensure a safe and effective therapeutic regimen. The goal of PC is to optimize the patient's quality of life and achieve good clinical outcomes.*

A. Analysis Method

The analytical method in statistics that is widely used in analyzing research results and observations is the *analysis of variance* (ANOVA) method. One type of ANOVA analysis that will be used in this study is one-way ANOVA analysis or also known as *one-way ANOVA*. The *one-way ANOVA* method is a tool that is used to simultaneously test whether a population has the same mean value.

One-way ANOVA analysis can be formulated as equations 1 and 2.

- Reject H₀ (accept H₁) if the P-value < Significance level
- Reject H₁ (accept H₀) if the P-value > Level of significance : Level of significance ($\alpha = 0.5$)

The rejection of H₀ indicates that there is a significant difference between the group mean values of the test variables, so the conclusion used is based on the H₁ hypothesis.

This analysis is a description or explanation using a table. The data were grouped and analyzed based on the answers to the questionnaires obtained from the respondents' responses using data tabulation. In this analysis, it will be

explained how the actual condition of each variable is. The analysis process is as follows:

➤ *Data verification*

That is re-checking the questionnaire that has been filled out by the respondent to ensure whether all statements have been completely answered by the respondent.

- Calculating the Value of Respondents' Answers The results of respondents' answers that need to be calculated.
- Calculate the TCR value of each category.

Formula :

$$TCR = RS/n \times 100$$

Description :

TCR = Level of attainment of respondents' answers

RS = Average score

n = Number of answers

Percentage of Achievement Criteria

TCR value 90% - 100% : Very good

TCR value 80% - 89.99% : Good

TCR value 65% - 79.99% : Enough

TCR value 55% - 64.99% : Not good

TCR Value 0% - 54.99% : Not Good

II. RESEARCH METHODS

This research is non-experimental research in the form of descriptive and quantitative analysis research with research instruments used in the form of a questionnaire. Research variables related in this study are *independent variables* in the form of gender, tenure, age, employment status. The dependent variable (*dependent variable*) is the doctor's perception of the role of pharmacists in pharmaceutical services.

The collection of demographic questionnaires in the form of gender, tenure, age and employment status was carried out using a questionnaire to doctors. The questionnaire used in this study are:

Doctor's Perception Questionnaire About the Role of Pharmacists in Pharmaceutical Services (Prima et al, SCPIJ, 2017)

- Pharmacists regularly notify me if they find a clinical problem related to my prescription
- My experience, Pharmacists help me in choosing the right drug and designing treatment therapy for my patients
- My experience, Pharmacists monitor and follow the progress of my patient's condition and they will notify me if they find any drug related problems (eg adverse drug reactions, medication failure, etc.)
- In my experience, Pharmacists are ready to take personal responsibility for solving any drug-related problems they fin.

- Pharmacists often ask me to clarify the treatment goals I have in mind for my patients
- In my experience, Pharmacists are a trusted source of general drug information (ie drug facts that can be found in standard references)
- In my experience, Pharmacists are a trusted source for clinical drug information (ie information regarding clinical use of drugs in certain situations)
- Pharmacists regularly provide me with information about alternative drugs that are more effective and cost-effective for the drugs I prescribe
- Pharmacists regularly consult my patients regarding the safe and proper use of their medications
- 10. In my experience, pharmacists help improve patient compliance in medication
- The pharmacist adjusts my patient's medication with my consent (adjustments include dose adjustment, change of route of administration)
- My experience, Pharmacists help in educating and counseling my patients about disease, non-pharmacological therapy, lifestyle changes related to their disease
- In my experience, pharmacists are successful in helping patients choose the right non-prescription (OTC) drugs
- In my experience, pharmacists are successful in dealing with minor illnesses, such as minor illnesses such as fever, flu, etc., who can use drugs without a doctor's prescription.
- My experience, Pharmacists are successful in adapting drugs for patients with chronic diseases

III. RESEARCH RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The initial stage of the study began with making the percentage of the demographic characteristics of doctors at Tengku Rafi'an Siak Hospital and dr. Rasidin Padang from the results of the questionnaires that have been collected.

Karakteristik Demografi Dokter	Jumlah	
	Banyak	(%)
Jenis Kelamin		
Perempuan	31	53%
Laki-laki	28	47%
Umur		
21-30	12	20%
31-40	24	41%
41-50	16	27%
51-60	7	12%
Lama Kerja		
< 1 tahun	8	14%
2 -3 tahun	17	29%
> 4 tahun	34	58%

Table 1. Demographic Percentage of Doctors at Tengku Rafi'an Hospital Siak

Karakteristik Demografi Dokter	Jumlah	
	Banyak	(%)
Jenis Kelamin		
Perempuan	46	70%
Laki-laki	20	30%
Umur		
21-30	1	2%
31-40	24	36%
41-50	33	50%
51-60	8	12%
Lama Kerja		
< 1 tahun	0	0%
2-3 tahun	19	29%
> 4 tahun	47	71%

Table 2. Percentage of Demographic Doctors at RSUD dr.Rasidin Padang

The next stage is to conduct a Doctor's Perception Data Analysis Test about the role of pharmacists in pharmaceutical services at Tengku Rafi'an Hospital Siak and RSUD dr.Rasidin Padang using the average (mean) and standard deviation test method with the SPSS application.

A. Variable view of each variable.

Figure 1. Variable view of each variable.

B. Analysis Test Criteria

P1 – P15 = Questions Items Perception of Doctors on the Role of Pharmacists in Pharmaceutical Services
 TCR = Total Respondents Achievement

Percentage of Achievement Criteria
 TCR value 90% - 100% : Very good
 TCR value 80% - 89.99% : Good

TCR value 65% - 79.99% : Enough
 TCR value 55% - 64.99% : Not good
 TCR Value 0% - 54.99% : Not Good

C. The results of the analysis of doctors' perceptions about the role of pharmacists in pharmaceutical services based on gender in Tengku Rafi'an Hospital Siak and RSUD dr. Rasidin Padang

Statistics																
	P1	P2	P3	P4	P5	P6	P7	P8	P9	P10	P11	P12	P13	P14	P15	Gender
N Valid	12	12	12	12	12	12	12	12	12	12	12	12	12	12	12	125
Missing	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Mean	3.8	3.5	3.6	3.6	3.4	3.5	3.6	3.4	3.6	3.8	3.6	3.5	3.5	3.3	3.4	1.44
Std. Deviation	.84	.79	.87	.74	.86	.77	.81	.86	.81	.83	.93	.98	.75	.90	.92	.498

Figure 2. Statistics on the results of the analysis of doctors' perceptions about the role of pharmacists in pharmaceutical services by gender

From the data above, the value of $\bar{x} \pm SD$ for gender criteria is 1.44 ± 0.498 with a total TCR of 71.85, so it can be concluded that doctors' perceptions about the role of pharmacists in pharmaceutical services at Teuku Rafi'an Siak Hospital and dr. Rasidin Padang seen from the gender criteria is quite good.

D. The results of the analysis of doctors' perceptions about the role of pharmacists in pharmaceutical services based on length of service at Tengku Rafi'an Hospital Siak and RSUD dr. Rasidin Padang

Statistics																
	P1	P2	P3	P4	P5	P6	P7	P8	P9	P10	P11	P12	P13	P14	P15	Lama Kerja
N Valid	12	12	12	12	12	12	12	12	12	12	12	12	12	12	12	125
Missing	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Mean	3.8	3.5	3.6	3.6	3.4	3.5	3.6	3.4	3.6	3.8	3.6	3.5	3.5	3.3	3.4	2.22
Std. Deviation	.84	.79	.87	.74	.86	.77	.81	.86	.81	.83	.93	.98	.75	.90	.92	.537

Figure 3. Statistics on the results of the analysis of doctors' perceptions about the role of pharmacists in pharmaceutical services based on length of work

From the data above, the value of $\bar{x} \pm SD$ for the criteria for length of work is 2.22 ± 0.537 with a total TCR of 71.85, so it can be concluded that doctors' perceptions of the role of pharmacists in pharmaceutical services at Teuku Rafi'an Siak Hospital and dr. Rasidin Padang seen from the criteria for long working is quite good.

IV. CONCLUSION

Based on the results of observations during research and discussion, it can be concluded:

- From testing the data at two Regional General Hospitals (Teuku Rafi'an Siak Hospital and Dr. Rasidin Padang) the perception of doctors about the role of pharmacists in pharmaceutical services is quite good.
- Doctors' perceptions of the role of pharmacists in pharmaceutical services are also influenced by the level of local hospital accreditation.
- Doctors' perceptions about the role of pharmacists in pharmaceutical services at Tengku Rafi'an Hospital Siak tend to be good, so the performance of pharmacists in pharmaceutical services is very helpful for medical services at the hospital.
- The tendency of doctors' perceptions about the role of pharmacists in pharmaceutical services that are not good must collaborate and synergize to create even better services.

SUGGESTION

Based on the conclusions in this study, the researchers provide the following suggestions:

- It is hoped that further researchers will take samples with more sample validity.
- It is hoped that further researchers will examine doctors' perceptions of pharmaceutical services more deeply so that more complete results are obtained on this matter.
- It is expected that data testing (Data Analysis Test) uses other methods.
- In taking the object of research, look for hospitals that have been accredited A.

LIMITATION

- Data analysis in the study of doctors' perceptions of the role of pharmacists in pharmaceutical services used the one-way analysis method (*one way ANOVA*).
- Sampling of research on doctors' perceptions of the role of pharmacists in pharmaceutical services using the census method.
- The object of research on doctors' perceptions about the role of pharmacists in pharmaceutical services is the Regional General Hospital (RSUD) which has not been accredited A.

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